

TEACHING VOCABULARY IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE NO PHILOLOGY DIRECTIONS

Tojibayeva Nazokat

Doctor of pedagogical Sciences (PhD) of the Department of Foreign Language in Exact And Natural Directions of Tashkent State Pedagogical University

To`lanova Muxlisa

Student of the Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami

Saxobiddinov Nuriddin

Student of the Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami

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Abstract. *This article about English has become a universal and dominant source to communicate in the world, the interest of learning this language is increasing dramatically. But people can't use any languages without vocabulary and this paper analyses the vocabulary of a language and vocabulary teaching methods and techniques and studies some methods.*

Keywords: *research, methodologies, tradition, theory and practice, actual objects, recommendation, encourage, analysis, wide variety, determining, skills.*

ПРЕПОДАВАНИЕ ЛЕКСИКИ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА В НЕФИЛОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯХ

Аннотация. *Эта статья об английском языке стала универсальным и доминирующим источником для общения в мире, интерес к изучению этого языка резко возрастает. Но люди не могут использовать никакие языки без словарного запаса, и в этой статье анализируется словарный запас языка, методы и приемы обучения словарному запасу, а также изучаются некоторые методы.*

Ключевые слова: *исследование, методология, традиция, теория и практика, актуальные объекты, рекомендация, поощрение, анализ, разнообразие, определение, навыки.*

Vocabulary and its related research paradigms have many inflections in relation to English language teaching. There is a long tradition of research into vocabulary acquisition in a second and foreign language. These include: classroom-based studies exploring different methodologies for vocabulary teaching; a long history of lexicographic research with reference to English dictionaries for language learners, research which has recently accelerated under the impetus of corpus-based, computer-driven lexical analysis; and new computer-driven descriptions of vocabulary which re-evaluate the place of words as individual units in relation to both grammar and the larger patterns of text organization. Central to research into vocabulary learning are key questions concerning how words are learned. Teachers help learners with vocabulary directly or 'explicitly' by means of word lists, paired translation equivalents and in variously related semantic sets. They also help learners by more indirect or 'implicit' means, such as exposure to words in the context of reading real texts. Over many years a key question asked by teachers and researchers is 'What does it mean to learn a word?' A definition of learning a word depends crucially on what we mean by a word, but it also depends crucially on how a word is remembered, over what period of time and in what circumstances it can be recalled and whether learning a word also means that it is always retained. Much work has therefore involved issues of memorization, and important questions have been raised concerning whether the

storage of second language (L2) words involves different kinds of processing from the storage of first language (L1) words. Craik and Lockhart have been particularly influential in showing how processing of words at different levels is crucial to learning. By different 'levels' is meant integration in the learning process of sound levels, visual shape and form, grammatical structure and semantic patterns so that processing occurs in 'depth' and not just superficially as may be the case, for example, if a word is learned only in relation to its translation equivalent. We have not been taught the majority of words which we know. Beyond a certain level of proficiency in learning a language - and a second or foreign language in particular - vocabulary development is more likely to be mainly implicit or incidental. In vocabulary acquisition studies one key research direction is, therefore, to explore the points at which explicit vocabulary learning is more efficient than implicit vocabulary learning, to ask what are the most effective strategies of implicit learning, and to think the implications of research results for classroom vocabulary teaching. In the late 1980s and 1990s research in these areas developed rapidly. Researchers continue to question what exactly is meant by terms such as 'efficient' and 'effective' in short-term and long-term vocabulary learning. Also, recognition of the importance of implicit vocabulary learning does not preclude continuing exploration of how explicit vocabulary learning can be enhanced. N. Ellis identifies four main points on an explicit-implicit vocabulary-learning continuum:

A strong implicit-learning hypothesis holds that words are acquired largely by unconscious means. A weak implicit-learning hypothesis holds that words cannot be learned without at least some noticing or consciousness that it is a new word which is being learned. A strong explicit-learning hypothesis holds that a range of metacognitive strategies such as planning and monitoring are necessary for vocabulary learning; in particular, the greater the depth of processing involved in the learning, the more secure and long term the learning is likely to be. Note, however, that their findings have not been unequivocally accepted or agreed with. At advanced levels reading by means of inferential strategies may therefore be central to vocabulary development. At beginning levels, strategies of rote memorization, bilingual translation and glossing can be valuable in learning, e.g., phonetic and graphological shapes and patterns of words. In learning the surface forms of basic concrete words, explicit learning may be the best route. However, for semantic, discursal and structural properties of less frequent, more abstract words, implicit learning may be better. Recent vocabulary acquisition research suggests strongly that the explicit-implicit vocabulary-learning continuum is a good basis for research. Language description will continue to involve computational processing of millions of words, providing hitherto unseen pictures of languages.

In particular, more information will be available concerning patterns of fixed expressions, leading to more dictionaries which assist learners with the collocational and idiomatic character of English. Increasing numbers of corpora of spoken English will allow comparisons between spoken and written forms and be of use to learners in the development of formal and informal lexico-grammatical usage. Indeed, dictionaries will probably include ever more grammatical information, just as grammars will include ever more lexical information. In parallel with these developments lexis acquisition research is likely to include greater reference to issues of learning word units as well as individual words, describing and accounting for the incremental stages of words, word families, lexicogrammatically phrases and word networking which learners pass through as they gain greater L2 lexical competence. In summary, vocabulary

teaching and learning is central to the theory and practice of English Language Teaching. Words have a central place in culture, and learning words is seen by many as the main task in learning another language. Interest in vocabulary – from researchers, teacher – researchers – is likely to continue to grow apace.

Therefore, the study of vocabulary is at the center while learning a new language. No matter English being a second language or foreign language, one needs to learn vocabulary in the systematic way. If we purpose to utilize language effectively and clearly, we ought to have good stock of vocabulary. Especially the English language is the richest to words. Thornburg opines: "If you spend most of your time studying grammar, your English will not improve very much. You will see most improvement, if you learn more words and expressions. You can say very little with grammar, but you can say almost anything with words." In accordance with his point of view, nowadays modern pedagogy faces some challenges how to develop teaching abilities, methods and innovative techniques of vocabulary as well as using words in real life. Because of modern researches observations and experiences learners can be educated by teachers better by teachers and in the following some useful types of methods will be introduced in order to achieve more interesting and qualitative lessons.

1. Actual objects and showing models.

This technique brings a lot of profits to teach vocabulary to the beginners. The names of many things can be taught by showing actual objects. It gives real experience and sense to the learners. For example, pen, chalk, table, chair, book, football, flowers, tomato etc. which are every pupil have in their bags or home, can be taught in the classroom. Real objects or models of real objects are very effective

and meaningful in showing meanings .by this method pupils can memorize new words easily due to their actuality.

2. Synonyms

Using synonyms are really suitable way to improve vocabulary of young learners. A synonym may be used to help the student to figure out the different shades of meaning, if the synonym is better known than the word being taught. Synonyms assist to enrich a student's vocabulary bank and provide alternative words instantly. These can be effective since they build on words and phrases that students already recognize. Also, synonyms serve not only to create very attractive and peculiar conversation but also every user can remember every word faster and try to use and search yourself more academic and meaningful equivalent of a word. This style is also recommended even for future IELTS (International English Language Testing System) candidates to increase their vocabulary. Because according to the requirements of all parts of the IELTS exam, every candidate must show his or her ability to use different words in their vocabulary bank in order to higher mark. Besides that, as a supportive source of this method creative educators could make crosswords, word snakes or other puzzles for students with using these synonyms.

3. Homonyms

Homophones are words of the same language that are pronounced alike even if they distinguish in spelling, meaning, or origin, such as "pair" and "pear". Homophones may also be spelled alike, as in "bear" (the animal) and "bear" (to carry). But this list consists only of homophones that are not spelled alike. This approach is really important to enhance vocabulary

bank of students as well as their pronunciation. In the table there are some examples of homonyms:

ant/aunt eye/I
ate/eight fare/fair
bear/bare sea/see
son/sun stationary/stationery
steal/steel threw/through
throne/thrown be/bee
blew/blue by/bye/buy
beach/beechnell/sell
cent/scent/sent census/senses
cereal/serial die/dye

This method is in really instructional and interesting to use in the classroom, because at one glance pupils will hurry to learn to pronounce and even translate their meaning.

3. Role play

Role-play is to create the presence of a real-life situation in the classroom. It is extremely important in the classroom communication because it gives students an opportunity to practice communicatively in different social contexts and in different social roles. The language applied in this activity is varied according to the student's status, attitudes, mood, and different situations. Furthermore, role - play help to cultivate the sense of interest to art, culture, traditions that are influential to their behavior as well as student can learn how to use new words in real life.

Because, little pieces of dramas or plays are demonstrated as a real and live. In 2006, linguist Blachowicz stated that, "Teachers can introduce some of the words which provide both definitional and contextual information about the words to be learned by making up a dialogue for students so that students can understand a further meaning and usage of the words."

4. Video to produce of target vocabulary.

To utilize this approach educators are required to select a video segment that contains a series of actions or visual detail according to their age, level of knowledge, interest, gender, outlook and religion. Richards said "When vocabulary words are being taught to pupils, teachers need to consider how to teach these words to pupils based on the levels of ages, educational background and field of interest. Next step is providing the learners with a list of target vocabulary words and ask them to construct a paragraph that incorporates as many of the words as possible. This activity is best done after the learners have seen the video. As they learn how to use more vocabulary properly, teacher will see an improvement in their writing and speaking. As a role of "Resource" teacher can also show a short film without sound and asking pupils to discuss what dialogue they would expect to hear. Showing a scene from a film without sound and asking pupils to use the facial expression to determine emotion. Videos may be different such as parts of films, news comics or even short cartoons that can introduce new words.

Moreover, according to statistics the amount of vocabulary that children need to acquire each year is staggering in scope, estimated to be about 3,000 words a year. Therefore, a comprehensive approach was introduced to pedagogy which consists of the following components needs to be in place.

- Use "instructional" read-aloud events. The recommendation that parents and teachers read aloud to children is among the most popular recommendations in the field of reading.

• Systematically teach students the meaning of prefixes, suffixes, and root words. The majority of English words have been created through the combination of morphemic elements, that is, prefixes and suffixes with base words and word roots. Anderson and Freebody claimed that "If learners understand how this combinatorial process works, they possess one of the most powerful understandings

necessary for vocabulary growth. "By this idea it is clarified that using prefixes, suffixes, and root words to develop target vocabulary can accelerate learning process of new words.

10 Principles for Effective Vocabulary Instruction (and 10 Things to Avoid!)

<p>DO THIS</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Select words to teach. 2. Use strategies to engage students in word study. 3. Help students to come up with their own definitions. 4. Assess student use of words in authentic writing and speaking. 5. Teach students morphological strategies to figure out words they do not know in addition to context-clue strategies. 6. Use symbols and pictures to help bring vocabulary to life. 7. Highlight and use a word wall in classroom instruction. 8. Use and apply vocabulary words regularly (versus isolated practice). 9. Allow opportunities for wide reading so students are exposed to words all the time in a variety of books. 10. Model the use of academic language of all tones, setting high expectations for language use. 	<p>NOT THAT</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Assign long lists of words (six to eight a week is recommended) but never teach about the words selected. 2. Have students look up lists of words in a dictionary, write arbitrary sentences, or copy words multiple times. 3. Have students simply copy definitions. 4. Give students matching tests that show only misspellings of definitions. 5. Tell students to use only context clues to figure out unknown words. 6. Lock the use of visual aids in the classroom to assist with vocabulary instruction. 7. Lock or misuse a word wall in the classroom. 8. Spend a large chunk of language arts time working on vocabulary in isolation. 9. Teach only whole-class books/texts with centralized vocabulary study. 10. Use "kiddo" language around students and allow students to speak "kiddo" back.
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Vocabulary Cubes

First Dice Words

Both partners choose the same 6 words to practice, then write a word on each line. Do not let your partner see the order of your words. Your partner should figure out your word from the strategy you use.

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____
4. _____
5. _____
6. _____

Second Dice Strategies

- 1 = Make a connection to another word
- 2 = Give your definition of the word
- 3 = Draw the word
- 4 = Act it out
- 5 = Give a synonym or antonym
- 6 = Use the word in a sentence

As teachers, you know teaching vocabulary is important, but you need ways to make it stick. One-way elementary students learn is with visuals, but you may wonder how to teach vocabulary by using pictures?

When you are planning your vocabulary lessons, look for pictures that are kid-friendly and high-interest to make connections to the words. Children love to see pictures of animals in the wild and other children their age, whether it is a real or drawn image. Tie a story to the image to engage students' memory muscles. Readers learn so much from pictures and words together. See more here about the different kinds of pictures you can use to teach vocabulary.

By the way of conclusion, it should be mentioned that, there is no sure-fire remedy or method to enhance vocabulary in a day or two. A student's vocabulary bank can be enriched on a gradual basis and one should always show keen interest and enthusiasm in finding, learning and understanding new words. Teaching vocabulary through incidental, intentional, and independent approaches requires teachers to plan a wide variety of activities and exercises.

REFERENCES

1. Khodjamkulov, U., Makhmudov, K., & Sokurov, A. (2020). The Issue of Spiritual and Patriotic Education of Young Generation in the Scientific, Political and Literary Heritage of Central Asian Thinkers. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(05), 6694-6701.
2. Makhmudov, K. (2020). Ways of Forming Intercultural Communication in Foreign Language Teaching. *Science and Education*, 1(4), 84-89.
3. Makhmudov, K. (2020). Current Problems of Teaching English and New Approaches to Resolve in Secondary Education Schools. *Modern Trends in Linguistics: Problems and Solutions*, 271-273.
4. ALTA ESL Book Center Publishers. <http://www.altaesl.com/index.cfm>.
5. Cambridge University Press. <http://uk.cambridge.org/>